

MARKETING BEHAVIOUR OF COCONUT GROWERS IN KANYAKUMARI DISTRICT

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Abstract:

The study was undertaken with the objectives of marketing behaviour of coconut growers in Kanyakumari district. The study was taken-up in Kanyakumari district of Tamil Nadu. Out of the nine blocks in Kanyakumari district, Rajakkamangalam block was selected based on the maximum area under coconut cultivation. A sample size of 120 coconut cultivating farmers was selected by using proportionate random sampling technique. The required data were collected by personal interview utilising a well structured and pre-tested interview schedule. The result revealed, that nearly sixty per cent of the respondents (58.33 per cent) had medium level of marketing behaviour, whereas 25.00 per cent of the respondents had high level of marketing behaviour, while 16.67 per cent of the respondents possessed low level of marketing behaviour.

Introduction:

Development of any economy depends primarily on the important role played by entrepreneurs. Their importance is much more vital in a developing country like India, where there is ample opportunity for using innovations to exploit the available resource. Thus, in all economic development activities more and more emphasis is being given on entrepreneurship of people. Entrepreneur play a pivotal role in catalysing economic growth of a country and the same is recognised world over. This is because entrepreneurs are by nature job-creators instead of job seekers. They are also innovators who increase the productivity of business enterprise they established. Entrepreneurship plays a critical role in the growth of India, which has abundance of natural and human resources. Besides, being the vehicle of agricultural development, entrepreneurship can solve acute problem like unemployment, concentration of wealth in few selected hands, imbalance in regional development, increasing wastage of youth in destructive activities, etc., Agriculture oriented occupations promote the national economy and these occupations are becoming more complex and complicated and therefore development of entrepreneurial ability is a key to face problems. All these factors call for development of entrepreneurship on the part of farmers to survive and succeed in the present day world of competition. Keeping these things in view, the objectives were set to study the marketing behaviour of coconut growers in Kanyakumari district.

Methodology:

The study was taken-up in Kanyakumari district of Tamil Nadu. Out of the nine blocks in Kanyakumari district, Rajakkamangalam block was selected based on the maximum area under coconut cultivation. A sample size of 120 coconut cultivating farmers was selected by using proportionate random sampling technique. The required data were collected by personal interview utilising a well structured and pre-tested interview schedule. The collected data were tabulated and analysed using appropriate statistical tools. Marketing behaviour referred to the capacity or tendency of an individual farmer to identify the market trend to sell the produce for greater return. In this study marketing behaviour was studied six dimension viz., the time of sale, place of sale, mode of sale, mode of transport, selling pattern of farm produce and source of market information. The marketing behaviour for measured through percentage analysis.

Findings and Discussions:

Marketing Behaviour of Coconut Growers:

The marketing behaviour of the respondents in the activities related to coconut crop have been analysed individually and discussed. Further, their dimension of marketing behaviour viz., time of sale, place of sale, mode of sale, mode of transport, selling pattern and source of market information was assessed and results are presented in following Table-1-7.

Overall Marketing Behavior:

The data on overall marketing behaviour adopted by the respondents are presented in Table-1. The respondents were categorised into three levels viz., low, medium and high based on the cumulative frequency methods, the results are presented in Table-1.

Table 1: Distribution of respondents according to their overall marketing behaviour

(n=120)

S.No	Category	Number	Percent
1	Low	20	16.67
2	Medium	70	58.33

3	High	30	25.00
Total		120	100.00

It could be observed from the Table -1, that nearly sixty percent of the respondents (58.33 per cent) had medium level of marketing behaviour, whereas 25.00 percent of the respondents had high level of marketing behaviour, while 16.67 per cent of the respondents possessed low level of marketing behaviour. Hence, it could be concluded from the Table-1, that majority of the respondents had medium level of marketing behaviour to high level. This may be due to the fact that the most of the coconut growers were found to increase their income level manifold and contributed to the development of their family. In this process, most of the respondents reported that they were actively participated in time of sale, place of sale, mode of sale, mode of transport, selling pattern of farm produce and source of market information. This would have result with majority of the coconut growers fell under medium level of marketing behaviour. This finding is in line with the findings of Prathapsingh (2012) who also reported that majority of the respondents had medium level of marketing behaviour in banana cultivation.

Dimension of Marketing Behavior:

This section deals with the results obtained among coconut growers with respect to individual dimensions of marketing behaviour. The results obtained in this regards are presented in Table from 2-7

Time of Sale:

The distribution of respondents according to their time of sale are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Distribution of respondents according to their time of sale

(n=120)

S.No	Category	Number	Percent
1	Soon after harvest	70	58.34
2	When the price is attractive	40	33.33
3	When in need of cash	10	8.33
Total		120	100.00

It could be seen from the table 2, that nearly sixty per cent of the respondents (58.34 percent) sold their produce immediately after harvest. Whereas, one-third of the respondents (33.33 percent) sold their produce when the price is attractive in the market. Only 8.33 percent of the respondents sold their produce when in need of cash. The small and marginal farmers, who would be normally to sold their produce after harvest immediately, because they want money for meet their farm and home expenses and also settling their loans. This might have been the major factors influencing a majority of them belonged to soon after harvest. The finding derives support from that of Janusia (2017) who also reported that similar findings in her research study of communication and marketing behaviour of coconut growers.

Place of Sale:

Distribution of respondents according to their place of sale are presented in Table 3

Table 3: Distribution of respondents according to their place of sale

(n=120)

S.No	Category	Number	Percent
1	In the village market	18	15.00
2	Market in the nearby town	37	30.83
3	Market in the distance town	65	54.17
Total		120	100.00

It is evident from the data in Table-3, that more than fifty per cent of the respondents (54.17 percent) had sold their produce in the distance town followed by 30.00 percent of the respondents had sold their produce in the nearby town market. Only 15.00 percent of the respondents had sold their produce in the village market. Hence, it could be concluded that majority of the coconut growers sold their produce in distance town. This might be due to reason that respondents may get more profit compared to the village market. This finding is in conformity with the findings of Janusia (2017) who also reported that majority of the coconut growers to sold their produce in distance town.

Mode of Sale:

To know about the people to whom the farmers sell their produce. The data were collected and presented in table 4.

Table 4: Distribution of respondents according to their mode of sale

(n=120)

S.No	Category	Number	Percent
1	Local traders	16	13.33
2	Regulated markets	9	7.50
3	Commission agent	29	24.17
4	Retailers	36	30.00

5	Whole salers	30	25.00
Total		120	100.00

A glance at the data in Table 4 showed that 30.00 per cent of the respondents had sold their produce to the retailer followed by whole saler (25.00 percent), commission agent (24.16 percent), local traders (13.33 percent) and regulated market (7.50 percent). It may be due to the fact that the respondents selling the product for a higher price per unit than the whole salers. The coconut growers will have face to face contact with customer and other members of the social system, helping people understand the work involved in production and sale. Thus, it may be concluded that majority of the respondents were found to have sold their produce to the retailer. This finding is in line with the findings of Dutta and Hazarika (2014) who reported that most of the respondents had sold their produce to the retailers.

Mode of Transport:

To know about the mode of transport used by the respondents, if the market is available outside from their village. The data were collected and presented in Table -5.

Table 5: Distribution of respondents according to their mode of transport

(n=120)

S.No	Category	Number	Percent
1	Head Load	-	-
2	Bicycle	9	7.50
3	City Bus	32	26.67
4	Tempo	51	42.50
5	Bullock Cart	-	-
6	Lorry	28	23.33
Total		120	100.00

It could be found from the Table 5, that majority of the respondents (42.50 percent) used tempo as a mode of transport to sell their produce in the market followed by 26.67 percent used city bus, 23.33 percent and 7.50 percent who used lorry and bicycle respectively. None of the respondents used head load and bullock cart to sell their produce in market. Hence, it could be interpreted that majority of the respondents utilise tempo as their mode of transport and city bus are perceived as easily available transport by the coconut growers. From the above finding, it could be observed that majority of them using tempo and city bus as their mode of transport. This might be due to good road connectivity to all villages and towns. So, the coconut growers select the road transport to sold their produce. This finding is in line with the findings of Janusia (2017).

Selling Pattern of Farm Produce:

To know about the selling pattern of farm produce. The data were collected and presented in Table-6.

Table 6: Distribution of respondents according to their selling pattern of farm produce

(n=120)

S.No	Category	Number	Percent
1	Raw Material	120	100.00
2	Processed Material	-	-
Total		120	100.00

From the Table 6, it could be seen that regarding the selling pattern of farm produce cent per cent of the respondents sell their produce as raw material. The possible reason they want immediate payment for their produce because to fulfill their needs and urgent concerns. Hence, it could be concluded that all the coconut growers sell their produce as raw material. This finding is in line with the findings of Janusia (2017) who also reported that majority of the respondents had sell their produce as a raw material in her study of communication and marketing behaviour of coconut growers.

Source of Market Information:

To analyse the various sources utilized by the respondents for getting information about marketing of their produce data were collected and presented in the Table-7.

Table 7: Distribution of respondents according to their source of market information

(n=120)

S.No	Category	Number	Percent
1	Relatives and friends	60	50.00
2	Local marketing centres	10	8.34
3	Regulated market	1	0.83
4	Commission agent and brokers	25	20.83
5	Retailers	6	5.00
6	Agricultural extension agents	10	8.34
7	News papers	6	5.00
8	All India Radio / Doordarshan	-	-

9	Internet- agriculture website	2	1.66
Total		120	100.00

It could be observed from the Table 7, that a half of the respondents (50.00 percent) received market information from their relatives and friends followed by 20.83 percent of the respondents had received information from commission agent and brokers, 8.34 percent of the respondents had received information from agricultural extension agents and local market centers respectively. Remaining categories of the respondents obtained information from retailers, newspapers, internet and regulated market with the percentage of 5.00, 5.00, 1.66 and 0.83 percent respectively. The findings revealed that most commonly used personal- localite channels for getting market information by the coconut growers were family members, relatives and friends. This might be due to the close proximity and frequent interaction. Hence, it may be concluded that a majority of the respondents received market information from their relatives and friends. This finding derives support from that of Janusia (2017) who also reported that majority of the respondents had used similar source for getting market related information.

Conclusions:

The coconut growers are found to possess medium level of marketing behaviour. Hence, it should be definitely noted down by planners and policy makers at state and district level to make arrangement for marketing the products for maximum price. It is also necessary to streamline all the marketing channels properly in order to reduce the constraints faces by the coconut growers in marketing and produce. An effective marketing strategy also needs to be framed by the state department of agriculture in co- ordination with the regulated markets, commission agents and other marketing organisations functioning at village level. There is a need to establish a separate co-operative society and regulated market exclusively for coconut growers.

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